

D5.6 POLICY BRIEF

Strengthening
Transatlantic Collaboration for
the Next Generation Internet

December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

INDEX

1. Executive Summary
2. Introduction & Context
3. Methodology & Sources of Evidence
4. Key Findings: Transatlantic Collaboration
5. The On-Campus Programme: Impact & Lessons Learned
6. Administrative & Operational Lessons Learned
7. Systemic Barriers for Transatlantic NGI Collaboration
8. Policy Recommendations
9. Conclusion

1. Executive Summary

NGI Sargasso has acted as a pioneering mechanism within the Next Generation Internet (NGI) initiative, promoting collaboration between the European Union, the United States, and Canada. Through multiple Open Calls, the programme funded and supported startups, SMEs and other entities developing human-centric internet technologies, while experimenting with a trilateral collaboration model.

Beneficiary feedback confirms that NGI Sargasso:

- accelerated the technical and business maturity of participating projects,
- expanded their international networks and visibility, and
- provided highly valued coaching, training, and on-campus support.

At the same time, structural barriers emerged clearly: regulatory divergence, funding asymmetries (especially for US and Canadian partners), and operational constraints linked to tight timelines and complex open call cycles.

This policy brief summarises:

- what worked particularly well in NGI Sargasso,
- where improvements are needed in programme design and administration, and
- how future EU–US–Canada NGI collaborations can be structured to be more effective and inclusive.

2. Introduction & Context

The NGI initiative supports the development of a more resilient, trustworthy, and user-centric internet, grounded in European values. NGI Sargasso contributed to this mission by funding EU-based innovators and requiring them to collaborate with partners from the US and/or Canada.

This trilateral requirement:

- brought different innovation ecosystems into direct contact,
- enabled beneficiaries to test their ideas against multiple regulatory and market realities, and
- created opportunities for joint research, experimentation, and knowledge exchange.

However, the programme also surfaced systemic obstacles: differences in legal and regulatory frameworks, lack of direct financial incentives for non-EU partners, and an innovation environment in Europe where small businesses often have fewer access points to incubators, private investors, and venture capital than in the US. In this context, programmes like NGI Sargasso are particularly crucial for EU startups and SMEs, which may not be well positioned to access large-scale schemes such as Horizon Europe on their own.

3. Methodology & Sources of Evidence

This brief is based on a combination of quantitative and qualitative inputs, including:

- Post-programme surveys completed across all beneficiary cohorts.
- Team performance evaluations and feedback collected at multiple stages of the programme.
- A dedicated **Survey to US and Canadian counterparts**, collecting views on collaboration with Europe, perceived regulatory and funding barriers, and expectations for future cooperation.
- A workshop with external experts on transatlantic NGI collaboration.
- Direct communication with beneficiaries throughout the project.
- Two dedicated NGI coordinators' meet-ups, where experiences and lessons learned across NGI projects were exchanged.
- Internal debriefings with the NGI Sargasso consortium partners on administrative procedures, coaching, on-campus design, open call operations and lessons learnt.
- Meetings organised with the National Science Foundation (US), Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (Canada) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA; US)

This multi-source approach ensures that the recommendations are grounded both in concrete beneficiary experience and in the operational reality of implementing such a programme.

4. Key Findings: Transatlantic Collaboration

4.1 What Worked Well

Across surveys and interviews, beneficiaries consistently reported that the trilateral structure added value to their projects by:

- bringing complementary expertise and different innovation cultures into the same project,
- creating genuine cross-border networking opportunities, and
- increasing their visibility in North American ecosystems.

For several consortia, NGI Sargasso was the reason the collaboration happened at all. In many cases, the programme served as a catalyst that turned informal connections or abstract interest in North America into concrete project partnerships.

4.2 Challenges Identified by Beneficiaries

Despite the value, several recurring challenges emerged:

- **Funding asymmetry:** only EU-based entities could receive cascade funding. US and Canadian partners repeatedly mentioned that lack of direct EU funding limited the resources they could commit and, in some cases, constrained their involvement.
- **Regulatory and legal differences:** divergent regulatory paradigms (e.g. GDPR and emerging EU legislation such as the Cyber Resilience Act) created uncertainty among US/CA partners about compliance and liability.
- **Administrative complexity:** although beneficiaries recognised improvements under Horizon Europe, some still perceived EU funding rules as demanding, which could be discouraging for non-EU organisations unfamiliar with them.
- **Time zone and coordination issues:** managing joint work across multiple time zones and organisational cultures required extra effort and careful planning.
- **Open source requirements vs commercialisation concerns:** the requirement that project results be open source was aligned with NGI goals, but some beneficiaries worried about safeguarding the commercial viability of their technical outputs.

4.3 What facilitates Collaboration

Several programme design features directly supported effective collaboration:

- **Dedicated help-desk:** a help desk responding within 72 hours provided rapid clarification on administrative, contractual, and procedural questions, which beneficiaries described as very helpful.
- **Consortium-level coordination:** strong collaboration within the organising consortium enabled continuous adjustment of the programme and quick responses to emerging issues.

- **Coaching and clear key performance indicators (KPIs):** individual coaching and definition of project-specific KPIs gave structure to collaborations and helped teams align expectations.
- **Iterative feedback loops:** constant feedback from beneficiaries and the consortium allowed the programme to evolve during implementation instead of remaining static.

5. The On-Campus Programme: Impact & Lessons Learned

5.1 Value for Beneficiaries

The On-campus programme was one of NGI Sargasso's most appreciated components. Beneficiaries highlighted that it:

- helped them become **market ready**, offering concrete tools to refine their business models, pitches, and go-to-market strategies;
- provided **inspiration talks and expert sessions** that broadened their vision beyond the purely technical aspects;
- delivered **marketing coaching**, which many teams particularly valued as they often lacked prior marketing knowledge;
- ensured **personalised follow-up** by assigning each project a dedicated coach who stayed with them throughout the full programme; and
- offered **visibility and networking opportunities**, including participation in high-profile events such as the Mobile World Congress, where many reported making strategic connections.

An additional benefit of the on-campus setup was the opportunity for **structured networking among funded beneficiaries**. These sessions led to peer learning, cross-project synergies, and collaborations beyond the initial consortium arrangements.

5.2 Role of Coaching and KPI Design

Survey feedback and internal evaluations showed very high satisfaction with the coaching team. A key lesson is that, when coach satisfaction is high, it is beneficial to **keep the same coaches throughout the programme**. Over time, they:

- become increasingly familiar with programme requirements and expectations, and

- accumulate knowledge of previous cohorts and recurring challenges, which they can then use to better support new teams.

Coaches played a central role in **co-defining individual KPIs** with each project. This process:

- encouraged teams to think outside the box about what success means,
- ensured that **dissemination and open-source-related KPIs** were included to support long-term sustainability of results, and
- helped balance **project-specific KPIs** with **general programme-level KPIs** that enable comparison across projects and foster knowledge transfer.
- This balance between individual and general KPIs was identified as a good practice that future programmes should maintain.

For instance, one beneficiary initially dreaded the requirement to conduct 40 industry interviews, but later described this experience as extremely beneficial: it forced the team to reach outside of its comfort zone, expand its network, and gather the feedback needed to fine-tune their solution.

5.3 Areas for Improvement in On-Campus Design

From the consortium's internal debriefing, several improvements emerged:

- Before launching the first Open Call, it is essential to **map the strengths, expertise, and training capacity of each consortium partner**, so that the on-campus curriculum is clearly aligned with what partners can realistically deliver.
- Training offers should match both the **maturity level of the projects** and **timeline and budget constraints**, to keep beneficiaries engaged and avoid content that feels either too basic or too advanced.
- Onboarding sessions should place stronger emphasis on **roles, responsibilities, and expectations**, especially around attendance to coaching, training, and other mandatory sessions.

6. Administrative & Operational Lessons Learned

6.1 Administrative Management

Administrative experience from NGI Sargasso suggests several actionable lessons:

- The **onboarding phase** should clearly spell out responsibilities and duties of both beneficiaries and the organising team, particularly around deadlines, reporting obligations, and participation in programme activities.
- A responsive **help-desk** (with a clear service standard, such as replies within 72 hours) is a key asset and should be explicitly resourced in future projects.
- Continuous, **two-way communication** between the consortium and beneficiaries allows for mid-course corrections rather than waiting until the end of the project.

6.2 Open Call Design & Implementation

From the operational side of the Open Calls, several points stand out:

- When a programme offers **different project lengths and different funding amounts**, guidelines and marketing materials should **explicitly incentivise shorter projects** as well, so that they do not appear less attractive or secondary.
- Before launching the first call, a **strict and realistic calendar** should be defined, taking into account any public holidays and existing commitments of consortium partners. Starting and ending dates significantly affect the quality of submissions and the feasibility of evaluations.
- The grant agreement should realistically **acknowledge time constraints**. Running too many calls in a short period (for example, five calls in three years) leaves limited room for iteration, learning, and fine-tuning calls based on previous experiences.
- Guidelines should clearly state that **beneficiaries can agree on their own on an ad hoc subdivision of funds with their transatlantic partners**, within the rules of the funding scheme. This can partially mitigate the lack of direct EU funding for non-EU partners and encourage more balanced consortia.

6.3 Marketing & Outreach

In terms of outreach:

- **Paid campaigns** did not perform as well as expected in terms of boosting the number of high-quality applications.
- More effective results came from **targeted, organic channels**, such as NGI and digital innovation networks, research communities, and diaspora or sector-specific networks in the US and Canada.
- Future programmes should allocate more effort to **curated, relationship-based outreach** and less to generic paid advertising.

7. Systemic Barriers for Transatlantic NGI Collaboration

NGI Sargasso's experience highlights structural issues that go beyond any single project's experience:

- **Regulatory divergence** (e.g. GDPR, cybersecurity legislation, product liability rules) continues to be perceived as a barrier by many US and Canadian actors.
- **Funding asymmetry**—with EU cascade funding limited to EU beneficiaries—reduces the incentives for North American partners to invest significant time and resources.
- **Fragmentation of funding information** makes it difficult for non-EU innovators to identify relevant opportunities to work with Europe.
- The requirement for **open-source results**, while aligned with NGI values, can sometimes be perceived as at odds with the commercialisation strategies of early-stage companies, and needs careful framing.

Addressing these barriers requires action at both EU and trilateral policy levels.

8. Policy Recommendations

8.1 Programme-Level Recommendations

At the level of future NGI-style cascade funding programmes:

- **Maintain long-term continuity of coaches** across cohorts to leverage accumulated programme knowledge and improve support quality.
- **Implement a balanced KPI framework**, combining project-specific KPIs with cross-programme KPIs for comparability and knowledge transfer.
- **Strengthen onboarding** with clearer responsibilities, duties, and attendance expectations for beneficiaries.
- **Provide a structured, responsive help desk** with a 72-hour maximum response time.
- **Introduce a voucher system** for events, travel, mentoring, and investor outreach (SFTP vouchers).
- **Allow clearly stated internal redistribution of funds** within consortia to support US/Canadian partners where legally possible.
- **Redesign training content based on maturity mapping**, ensuring sessions match project readiness levels.

- **Encourage short-term projects** by explicitly incentivising them when calls allow for multiple project durations.
- **Build in sufficient time between open calls** to learn, iterate, and relaunch (avoid overly compressed multi-call schedules).

Government and relevant agencies should be involved as early as the **grant agreement drafting phase**, to ensure that regulatory and funding realities are properly reflected and that national support instruments can be aligned where possible.

8.2 EU-Level Recommendations

At the EU policy level:

- **Create a curated, user-friendly EU funding portal**, cataloguing all relevant grants for EU and non-EU actors.
- **Ensure government involvement from the Grant Agreement stage**, enabling alignment of national support instruments and regulatory requirements.
- **Strengthen direct outreach in the US and Canada** through EU delegations, consulates, and diaspora networks.
- **Secure long-term continuation of NGI-style programmes**, essential for EU SMEs and startups lacking access to large-scale funds like Horizon Europe.
- **Develop new mechanisms to support non-EU partners**, such as associated-country schemes, bilateral funding envelopes, or cost-sharing tools.
- **Promote regulatory literacy on both sides**, through guides, briefings, and workshops on GDPR, CRA, and EU digital rules.
- **Support creation of transatlantic innovation hubs** focused on NGI technologies (AI, cybersecurity, interoperability, open source).

8.3 Trilateral (EU–US–Canada) Recommendations

To make transatlantic collaboration more systematic:

- **Establish a Trilateral NGI Cooperation Framework/Charter** with shared priorities, standards, and guiding principles.
- **Explore synchronised EU–US–Canada funding calls**, including models inspired by [NSF “Dear Colleague Letters.”](#)
- **Work toward mutual recognition or interoperability of standards** in cybersecurity, data governance, and digital trust.
- **Create a structured talent mobility scheme**, supporting short-term exchanges, residencies, and research visits between the three regions.

- **Promote a joint open-source innovation agenda**, ensuring sustainability while addressing commercialisation concerns from startups.

These measures would help move from ad-hoc collaboration to a more structured, predictable, and mutually beneficial transatlantic NGI ecosystem.

9. Conclusion

NGI Sargasso has demonstrated that trilateral collaboration on Next Generation Internet topics is both feasible and highly valuable. Beneficiaries improved their technological solutions, strengthened their business strategies, and expanded their networks well beyond their original geographical and sectoral boundaries.

At the same time, the project exposed structural issues—funding asymmetries, regulatory divergences, and operational constraints—that must be addressed if the full potential of transatlantic collaboration is to be realised.

Building on the lessons learned in NGI Sargasso, future programmes can:

- better support EU startups and SMEs,
- design more inclusive and effective collaboration models with US and Canadian partners, and
- contribute to a more open, trustworthy, and human-centric internet for all.